

Local Government in Croatia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Dario Runtic

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe
with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Croatia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Moritz Bechert/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Croatia: An Introduction

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

The Croatian intergovernmental legal framework contains a number of provisions related to distribution of competencies, local government autonomy, intergovernmental dialogue or consultation and legal remedies.

Croatia has ratified the European Charter for Local Self-Government in 1997 partially and 2008 fully. The Charter provides for full and exclusive transfer of competencies to the government level closest to the citizens, considering efficiency of service provision; adequate fiscal resources; consultation, supervision, right to associate, boundaries protection and legal protection.

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia provides a general competencies framework for local government which is further elaborated in the Law on Local and Regional Government and detailed in sectoral legislation. Distribution of fiscal resources, supervision and legal remedies are prescribed in the same fashion. In addition to general and detailed provisions, legal protection of local governments is additionally prescribed in constitutional law on Constitutional Court. Constitutional laws can be passed and amended by 2/3 majority of the parliament. Consultations among government levels and with the public are also prescribed in aforesaid legislation and further elaborated in the Law on Access to the Information. The right to associate is defined in the Law on Local and Regional Government, allowing local governments to establish national associations of local or regional governments should more than half of local or regional governments decide to do so.

The Croatian governance system is a three-tier system – national, regional and local government. National level counterparts in broadest terms are central government, legislature and judiciary. Regional government counterparts are primarily counties and their budgetary users. Local level counterparts are two distinct types of local governments – urban and rural - and their budgetary users and utility companies.

Intergovernmental relations in Croatia take various forms both in terms of vertical or horizontal relations. Having a three-tier governance system, vertical relations come in various forms from national to subnational, national to local, national to regional or regional to local, and vice versa, among any and all of aforesaid counterparts.

Horizontal relations are primarily any of the inter-municipal cooperation formats – joint utility companies, joint budgetary users or joint municipal departments or recently developed project agglomerations.

Most common vertical intergovernmental relations take place within legislative process framework and execution of competencies. Over the course of past few decades, the legislative process had undergone major changes in its form and dynamics. Some fifteen years of Croatian independence, the legislative process was mostly a national governance affair with rather limited input from the general public, which started to change during the following decade. Opening towards public input was of limited effect due to the fact that national government and parliament had to ramp-up the legislative process in order to timely adopt, transpose and implement EU *acquis communautaire*. Upon completion of adoption of the *acquis* and joining the EU, the legislative process decreased in pace allowing for substantial input from the general public and interested parties. An important cornerstone of the legislative process is the Parliamentary Board for Local Governments which involves members of the parliament as well as local and regional governments in discussion with the representatives of the government.

Aforesaid legislative process coupled with centralistic governance and fragmented subnational government had created an intertwined and overlapping matrix of competencies of three distinct levels of governance in public service provision. Such complex distribution of competencies, sometimes bordering with or crossing local autonomy lines, inevitably leads to intergovernmental issues and inefficiencies in public service provision. In such cases concerned levels of government often call for amendments to the legislation or legal remedies.

Intergovernmental judiciary relations are infrequent but tend to change the intergovernmental landscape when successfully executed by the local governments.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 4/2008 on Ratification of European Charter of Local Self-Government

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 2014

Law no 85/2015 on Access to the Information

Law no 73/2017 on Referenda and Other Means of Personal Participation in State and Local Affairs

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Kopric I, 'Widening the Scope of Local Self-Government Powers and Narrowing Central Government Supervision' (2000) *Hrvatska javna uprava* 391

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

